

borer, and leafhopper and moderate resistance to sheath rot, brown spot, and gall midge biotype 1.

Purnendu has strong seed dormancy for about 3 mo. Grain is golden with purple

apiculi. Mean grain dimensions are 7.9 × 2.8 mm with a test weight of 18.9 g. Kernels are white with a length-breadth ratio of 2.5. Hulling percentage is 79.5 and milling percentage is 73.5. Both alkali value (5.6)

and amylose content (26.1) are high.

A large amount of seed has been distributed through the minikit program to make the variety available to farmers. ■

Jitendra, a new deepwater rice variety for Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal, India

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The Varietal Identification Committee of the Indian Council of Agricultural Research approved the release in 1994 of Jitendra (SF432) for deepwater areas in Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal, India. Jitendra is a pureline selection from land races. It was developed at RRS, Chinsurah. The variety is suitable for water depths of 100 cm or more.

The mean yield of the variety in national trials was 2.8 t/ha with a yield potential of 5.0 t/ha. It yielded 46% more than Tilakkachari and 33% more than Jalmagna. It ranked third in the 1992 advanced variety trial-deepwater (AVT-DW), fifth in the 1991 AVT-DW, and seventh in the 1990 AVT-DW over the pooled means. At Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh, Jitendra yielded 5 t/ha in 1989 with a maximum water level of 191 cm, and 4 t/ha in 1992 when the maximum water depth was 141 cm (see table).

Jitendra is tall, photoperiod-sensitive, and flowers around the third week of October. It has tolerance for submergence, mainly through elongation and very good kneeing ability. Panicles are well exerted with long slender golden grains and purple apiculi. Grain dimension is 10.9 × 2.9 mm, with a test weight of 31.2 g. Kernels are white with a length-breadth ratio of 3.3. Hulling percentage is 79.7 and milling percentage is 72.5. The rice has intermediate alkali value (2.6) and amylose content (25.0). Seed dormancy is about 3 mo.

Jitendra has resistance to neck blast, brown planthopper, and whitebacked planthopper and moderate resistance to leafhopper and gall midge biotype 1. ■

Performance of Jitendra in national trials. India. 1988-92.

Year	Trial/site	Yield (t/ha)		Maximum water depth (cm)
		Jitendra	National check	
1988	<i>PVT-5^a</i>		<i>Tilakkachari</i>	
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.2 ^a	nil	85
	Pusa, Bihar	1.0*	nil	140
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	1.2	1.1	70
	Canning, West Bengal	3.1	3.6	90
1989	<i>UVT-6^b</i>		<i>Jalmagna</i>	
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	2.4	0.6	65
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	5.0	4.6	191
1990	<i>AVT-DM^c</i>			
	Pusa, Bihar	1.7	1.6	95
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.5	1.3	50
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	3.0*	2.1	200
1991	<i>AVT-DW</i>			
	Pusa, Bihar	2.4	2.2	na ^e
1992	<i>AVT-DW</i>			
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	4.0*	2.8	141
	Motto, Orissa	2.4	1.7	125

^aPVT-5 = Preliminary variety trial-5. ^bUVT-6 = Uniform variety trial-6. ^cAVT-DW = Advanced variety trial - deepwater. ^d* = significantly superior over national checks at the 5% level. ^ena = not available.

Seed technology

A simple method for producing F₁ hybrid seed for observational yield trials

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After good hybrid combinations are identified in test-cross nurseries, the next

step is to evaluate their performance in observational yield trials (OYT) before promoting the promising ones to regional or national trials.

With the numerous hybrids that need to be evaluated in OYT, it is often difficult to get proper space isolation to produce pure F₁ seed at a research farm. However, producing hand-crossed F₁ seed of many hybrids is laborious and often impractical. To overcome these problems, a simple method for producing a small quantity of relatively pure F₁ seed for conducting OYT was developed.

1. Layout for production of F₁ seed for observational yield trial.